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Abstract: Character is one of the main tools that serve to express the idea of the work. when creating a creative character, he imposes certain ideological goals on him, therefore, he is the product of long observations and great experience. In this article, various criteria and tasks of character are analyzed through Luqman Borikhon's novel "People in the Heat".

Key words: character, Aristotle, Poetics, 4 rules, purpose, originality, authenticity, consistency.

INTRODUCTION

Character is one of the phenomena that closely introduces the characters to the reader in the work, and causes the formation of a certain conclusion and imagination about them. In general, character refers to the characteristics of people, aspects that show their individuality, and just as there are no people with the same fingerprint in the world, there are no people with the same character, there can only be people with similar characteristics. In general psychology, character is defined as "a set of such psychological, subjective relationships in a person, which represent his attitude to existence, people, objective activity and himself." So, the character is mainly manifested in relationships. In the dictionary of literary studies, the scientific definition of character is given as follows: "Character (y. character - trace, sign, distinguishing feature) - artistic character; a human image that harmoniously embodies the most important general characteristics of people of a certain period and environment and individual characteristics of a particular person"[1; 354p.]. In fiction, various demands are placed on the character, ideological tasks are imposed.

MAIN BODY. The relationship to character was also important in ancient literature, and as proof of this we can see that Aristotle's Poetics (On the Fine Arts) focuses on the subject of character and explains its four purposes in detail. Aristotle says that the first and main goal of character is its nobility. In this case, the philosopher emphasizes that if a person has a certain goal in every word and action, it can be a character: "If a person aims for good goals, his character will also be good. It can exist in every person: a woman and even a slave may be good, the former may be worse (than a man), and a slave may be even worse" [2;40p.]. Of course, the writer imposes a certain spiritual idea on each character he introduces into the work, whether he is the main character or an episodic character, and in his place creates a suitable character image for this idea to emerge, Aristotle as written, character means purpose. In fact, character is a product of a person's inner world, a process that manifests his identity in his actions towards his goals. In his place, the writer, depending on whether the hero embodies the image of a good or bad person, infuses one of the negative or positive aspects into his character in a greater amount, thus creating different categories of characters that serve to express the idea of the work. Similarly, in the novel "People in the heat" by Luqman Borikhan, the old widow who was invited to a ceremony in the village does not say anything important in the work or does an important work, but her momentary appearance in the events of the work, the strange image of his appearance serves to reveal the main idea of the novel. That is, the young widow Lola Khan seems to see her future in the image of this old woman. The old woman who lives in so much honor and fame reveals the bitter truth to Lola Khan that she still has a small soul in her heart,

that she needs love and someone to lean on. No matter how much he is admired and appreciated by his loved ones, he is lonely at heart, thirsty for love. This aspect of the character, which has not lost its importance despite the passage of time, is an effective way to fulfill the task assigned to the hero. The second goal of the character, that is, its characteristic, is defined as its uniqueness: "Secondly, characters must be unique: a character can be brave, but a woman does not have courage and strength" [2;40p.] Of course, in differentiating between the king and the common people, in addition to their behavior, clothing, thinking, outlook, and speech are the main distinguishing tools, the differences between the images of women depicted in the same status in similar works are reflected in their character aspects. Uniqueness is one of the main criteria of character, and it requires great skill from the writer. After all, in order for a writer to create the image of a wrestler or a rider in his work, he must deeply study their character traits, their way of thinking and use them correctly. In particular, in the novel "People in the Heat", Luqman Borikhon tells the events of the work in the language of the boy Samad, describes them in an innocent, simple, funny way, similar to Samad's character and worldview, and tells the story of the events of the work in accordance with his character. In this place, Samad's character is different from that of his other peers, Tolqin or Durbek, and it is seen that Luqman Borikhon deeply analyzed the world of children of Samad's age and combined aspects that remind both children and adults in them. We are happy Or Shabnam and Lola Khan are both grown-up, loving, beloved girls, but their attitude towards love is reflected in their characters differently, that is, the uniqueness of the character, put Shabnam on one side and Lola Khan on the other. "Thirdly, the characters (life) must be truthful: this is absolutely different from what was said above, and it does not mean that they should be portrayed as good or handsome" [2;40p.]. In general, when creating a character, the artist summarizes and describes one or another aspect of people with different characteristics in life. In this process, in order to ensure the vitality of the character, he certainly cannot describe him without flaws and defects, otherwise, just as there is no absolute good or bad person in life, in the work an impeccable hero also exposes his fakeness, he cannot gain the reader's trust, therefore, Aristotle mentions the need to take this aspect into account when creating a character. In the same way, if in the novel, in the passage from the diary of Shunqor Hobil, there are no sentences indicating that Lola Khan is also a young widow thirsty for happiness, the reader will see Lola Khan as a "goddess who lives without needs", and that such people do not exist in real life, they exist only in fairy tales. I believe this could overshadow the success of the work. The fourth purpose or characteristic of character is called its consistency.

RESULTS. As a matter of fact, a great task is assigned to the character in a work of art, because the character of the hero is not only the character and aspects of a person, but also the features that serve to express the idea of the work, the author's intention, and give the breath of the society, era, and social existence in which the hero lives. and should embody it. "Indeed, character is the basis of a work of art. All actions and images are focused on revealing the essence of character" [3;160p.]. For this reason, character creation requires fine sensitivity, observation and skill from the writer. He should create or select character traits that are suitable for his character, in proportion to his profession, age, position in the work, and his role. However, when it comes to its place, it is necessary to show the level of character traits typical of an ordinary rider and the character of a chairman (L. Borikhon "People in the Heat").

CONCLUSION. That's why, "Character combines many elements of artistic creation (plot, composition, language) in itself, or rather forces it to "work" [4;48p.]. That is, if the character is a form in relation to the content of the work, then the plot, composition, language

(all tricks of the style) are a form in relation to the character. In fact, the character of the character is revealed in the development of the work's events, exposition, climax, conflict, author's or narrator's speech, portrait, dialogue, monologue, etc.

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